

Delay Minimization for Rate-Splitting Multiple Access-based Multi-Server MEC Offloading

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Abstract—Rate-Splitting Multiple Access (RSMA) has been recently recognized as a more general multiple access technique that overcomes the limiting factors of its predecessors related to the signal decoding complexity and interference management tradeoff. In this paper, we investigate the application of the RSMA technique to facilitate the users’ concurrent offloading to multiple servers in a multi-server Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) system. Each user fully offloads different parts of its computation task at the available MEC servers (or a combination of them) using the same frequency band. We aim to minimize the sum of users’ maximum experienced delay among the different MEC servers, stemming from both the offloading and processing, by jointly optimizing their computation task assignment ratios to the servers, their allocated common-message rates, common and private-message transmission powers, and computing resources related to each server. The formulated min-max-sum problem is non-convex, and its optimization variables are highly coupled. By examining its structure, we equivalently transform the problem and further decompose it into two independent sub-problems that separately provide solutions to the radio and computing resource allocation problems. Numerical results show the effectiveness of the proposed solution in terms of the users’ experienced delay and the proposed algorithm’s real execution time.

Index Terms—Delay Minimization, Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC), Rate-Splitting Multiple Access (RSMA).

I. INTRODUCTION

In light of the broader vision for digitalization and smart-X vertical industries (e.g., smart city, healthcare, manufacturing, transportation, education), the development of new localized Internet of Things (IoT) applications is rapidly growing, imposing strict computing and communication latency requirements to the network. As a means of delivering computing and caching services directly from the network edge, Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) has emerged, by the distributed deployment of MEC servers within the Radio Access Network (RAN) [1]. This reality allows mobile users to utilize

the different available RANs nearby and offload computation tasks of their compute-intensive and latency-critical applications to multiple MEC servers simultaneously. Apparently, the MEC paradigm has benefited from the advancements in next-generation multiple access techniques and the support for radio resource sharing among multiple concurrent user transmissions [2]. At the same time, however, this implies that MEC’s performance is majorly interwoven with the radio resource allocation, and thus should be studied jointly.

Recently, Rate-Splitting Multiple Access (RSMA) has been recognized as a promising multiple access technique in the direction of overcoming the limiting factors of its predecessor power-domain Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA), which are related to the signal decoding complexity and the interference management [3]. In the downlink RSMA, the message transmitted to multiple users is split into a common message and a private message. The common message is intended for and decoded by all the involved users in the transmission, whereas the private message is intended for each user separately. As a result, when decoding the private message, the interference stemming from the other users’ private messages is treated as noise. By intelligently and flexibly controlling the split among the common and private messages, RSMA strikes a good balance between efficient spectrum usage, interference management, and signal processing complexity, ameliorating the system’s performance [4].

In this paper, motivated by its good performance versus reduced complexity tradeoff, we envisage the application of the RSMA technique to facilitate MEC in the upcoming 6G wireless networks. Specifically, we apply the downlink RSMA principles to enable the users’ concurrent computation task offloading to multiple MEC servers. We design a holistic solution for the joint task offloading, and radio and computing resource allocation problem to minimize the sum of users’ maximum experienced delay among the different MEC servers, stemming from both the computation task offloading and processing. To this end, we jointly optimize the users’ computation task assignment ratios to the different MEC servers, and their allocated rates, uplink transmission powers, and computing resources with reference to the corresponding MEC server. It should be noted that this is the first attempt in the literature to exploit the benefits of the RSMA technique in a multi-server MEC setting.

A. Related Work

The problem of joint task offloading and resource allocation in MEC networks is well-established in the literature and

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has been extensively studied under different network settings and objectives over the years. Preliminary works focused on single-server network topologies, and can be further distinguished according to the adopted wireless access technique, i.e., Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) [5], power-domain NOMA [6], and Multi-Carrier (MC)-NOMA [7]. In [5], the joint problem of computation task assignment, computing resource allocation, and subcarrier allocation is treated via an iterative algorithm, to minimize the total MEC system's energy consumption. In [6], the authors consider a pure NOMA case and perform computation task assignment and uplink power control to minimize the maximum task completion time among the users. The formulated minimax optimization problem is then solved via a bisection search iterative algorithm. Complementary to the above, the work in [7] considers MC-NOMA and jointly optimizes the users' task offloading decision, subchannel assignment, uplink transmission power, and allocated computing resource to minimize the weighted sum of the system's computation time and energy overhead. Last, a comparative analysis over Orthogonal Multiple Access (OMA)-based and NOMA-based MEC systems is presented in [8] regarding the problem of minimizing the total system's energy consumption.

However, a remarkable amount of work can also be found on multi-server MEC network topologies, employing both OMA [9], [10] and power-domain NOMA [11]–[14]. Both works in [9], [10] account concurrently for multiple optimization objectives (e.g., minimization of MEC system's total time and energy overhead, users' subscription cost) and derive the task offloading decision and the power and computing resource allocation of the users. Considering the NOMA-based MEC topologies, the works in [11]–[13] target the MEC system's energy consumption minimization, whereas [14] pursues each user's maximum task completion time minimization among the different MEC servers. All of them optimize quite similar sets of variables but differ in the optimization techniques used such as Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithms apart from conventional optimization [11], the underlying network setting in terms of perfect or imperfect Channel State Information (CSI) [12], and the consideration of the additional problem of Central Processing Unit (CPU) frequency scheduling along [13]. Although multi-server MEC topologies are considered, the concurrent task offloading to multiple MEC servers is exclusively studied in [11], [12], [14], the former two of which focus on the sum system's energy consumption minimization. As a result, the problem of minimizing the sum of users' maximum experienced delay among multiple MEC servers that results in a min-max-sum problem formulation remains notably unexplored.

Regarding the literature around the RSMA technique, several works have been recently published dealing with fundamental problems related to resource allocation in pure wireless communication scenarios. Indicative examples constitute the works in [15]–[18], where the joint rate and power control are performed under different performance metrics. In [15] and [16], the sum-rate and weighted sum-rate maximization in downlink multi-user Single-Input Single-Output (SISO) and Multiple-Input Single-Output (MISO) systems are studied, re-

spectively, and two different iterative algorithms are proposed to obtain solutions to the formulated non-convex problems. The energy efficiency of a two-user downlink RSMA MISO system is pursued in [17], while another interesting approach towards controlling the spectral and energy efficiency tradeoff in a multi-user downlink RSMA Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) system appears in [18]. Moving one step further, the authors in [19] introduce the model of RSMA-based Simultaneous Wireless Information and Power Transfer (SWIPT) in MISO Broadcast Channels (BC) and study the precoder design of the Information Receivers (IRs) and the Energy Receivers (ERs) along with the common-message rate control problem to maximize the system's weighted sum rate.

Other attempts are gradually being made in the direction of exploiting the benefits of RSMA and supporting specific types of applications and services. For instance, in [20], the idea of integrating RSMA with Time Division Duplex (TDD) cell-free massive MIMO to support massive machine-type communications is investigated. Other applications of RSMA to a bistatic Dual-Functional Radar-Communication (DFRC) satellite system and a vehicular communication network aided by Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) and Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs) can be found in [21] and [22], respectively. Regarding the utilization of RSMA as a means of enabling the users' computation task offloading in MEC applications, only a limited number of works exists, i.e., [23], [24]. In [23], RSMA is used to assist MEC in a Cognitive Radio (CR) network, such that the secondary user avoids deteriorating the primary user's offloading by dynamically adjusting the rate-splitting parameters related to its transmission. In [24], a single-server MEC network is considered, where aerial users offload their tasks via RSMA, and the joint problem of offloading decision, rate, and uplink power control, and decoding order optimization is solved via a Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) method.

B. Contributions & Outline

In this paper, we capitalize on the ability to simultaneously access multiple servers in a multi-server MEC system and suggest the application of the novel RSMA technique, which is considered a key multiple access technique in the upcoming 6G wireless networks. Consequently, the challenging problem of joint computation task offloading and radio and computing resource allocation among the users and the multiple MEC servers arises, which remains mainly unsolved in the literature, and we strive to address it. The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows.

- 1) The problem of minimizing the sum of users' maximum experienced delay stemming from their task's offloading and processing among the different MEC servers is formulated. The aim is to jointly optimize the users' computation task offloading assignment ratios to the different MEC servers and their allocated rates, uplink transmission powers, and computing resources related to the corresponding MEC server.
- 2) The equivalent transformation of the initially formulated min-max-sum problem is analyzed to lead to an objec-

tive function of continuous form and derive the optimal conditions holding for the problem.

- 3) The Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions are employed to decompose the transformed problem into two independent sub-problems, the solutions of which separately provide suboptimal values for the radio (i.e., uplink transmission power and rate) and optimal values for the computing resource allocation. The optimal computation task assignment to the different MEC servers is also directly derived from the equivalent problem transformation and decomposition analysis.
- 4) Numerical results are obtained via modeling and simulation to demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed solution in terms of complexity and experienced delay by the users and to showcase the overall system's effectiveness against other traditional multiple access techniques.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. The system model is presented in Section II. The problem formulation, transformation, and decomposition are analyzed in Section III. The solutions to the computation task assignment and radio and computing resource allocation sub-problems are provided in Section IV. The simulation results are discussed in Section V and Section VI concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider an RSMA-based multi-server MEC system, as illustrated in Fig. 1, which consists of multiple MEC servers of potentially different computing capabilities that reside at the Base Stations (BSs) or the Access Points (APs) of the mobile network infrastructure. The MEC servers serve the purpose of offering computing services to the mobile users existing in the system. In this paper, we assume that each user fully offloads its computation task, due to the limited energy availability of the user device, while a combination of different available MEC servers can be chosen to process different parts of its computation task. Specifically, heavy Machine Learning (ML) tasks, e.g., image processing, can benefit from multi-server MEC offloading. Different video feeds generated from vehicular, healthcare, or security applications - to name a few - can be offloaded to different MEC servers for processing [25]. In this way, the total task complexity is reduced, and various levels of processing accuracy can be targeted for each part of the task based on each MEC server's computing capability.

Both the BSs or APs that host the MEC servers and the users are equipped with a single antenna. The overall system bandwidth is B Hz. To eliminate the inter-user interference in such a multi-user multi-server communication scenario, it is assumed that the users utilize separate frequency bands of bandwidth $B_n = \frac{B}{N}$ Hz to accommodate their computation task offloading, while a single user's transmissions to multiple MEC servers are performed concurrently and under the same frequency band, via the application of the RSMA technique.

We denote the set of MEC servers by $\mathcal{M} = \{1, \dots, M\}$ and the set of offloading users by $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, N\}$. A user's n computation task is defined as $C_n = \phi_n D_n$ [CPU cycles], where D_n [bits] and ϕ_n [CPU cycles/bit] denote the task's input data and intensity, respectively. In this paper, it is

Fig. 1: High-level overview of the multi-server MEC system.

considered that a task C_n can be arbitrarily partitioned into subsets of any size that, in turn, can be computed at different MEC servers. Specifically, we indicate as $\beta_{n,m} \in [0, 1]$ the user's n computation task assignment ratio to MEC server m , such that $\sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{n,m} = 1, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}$.

A. Communication Model

Concerning the RSMA-based communication model, we denote as $W_{n,m}$ the message of user n intended for MEC server m , containing the corresponding offloaded computation task $\beta_{n,m} C_n$. Each message $W_{n,m}$ is split into a common and a private part, i.e., $W_{n,m}^c$ and $W_{n,m}^p$, respectively. The common parts intended for all MEC servers from user n , i.e., $W_{n,1}^c, \dots, W_{n,m}^c, \dots, W_{n,M}^c$, are combined and encoded into a single common stream $s_{n,0}$ that is transmitted to all MEC servers with uplink transmission power $p_{n,0}$ [Watt]. The remaining private messages $W_{n,m}^p, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}$ are encoded into different private streams $s_{n,m}$ and are separately transmitted to the MEC servers with uplink transmission power $p_{n,m}$ [Watt]. Hence, the transmitted signal of user n is defined as:

$$x_n = \sqrt{p_{n,0}} s_{n,0} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sqrt{p_{n,m}} s_{n,m}. \quad (1)$$

The received signal at each MEC server m that is transmitted by user n is given by:

$$y_{n,m} = \sqrt{G_{n,m} p_{n,0}} s_{n,0} + \sum_{j=1}^M \sqrt{G_{n,m} p_{n,j}} s_{n,j} + z_{n,m}, \quad (2)$$

where $G_{n,m}$ denotes the channel gain between user n and MEC server m and $z_{n,m}$ is the corresponding Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) with zero mean and variance σ^2 .

Accordingly, the achievable rate of decoding the common stream $s_{n,0}$ transmitted by user n to each MEC server m is:

$$c_{n,m} = B_n \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{G_{n,m} p_{n,0}}{G_{n,m} \sum_{j=1}^M p_{n,j} + \sigma^2} \right) [bps]. \quad (3)$$

Without loss of generality, we consider that the channel gains between a user n and the offloading MEC servers are sorted in ascending manner, i.e., $G_{n,1} \leq \dots \leq G_{n,m} \leq \dots \leq G_{n,M}$. We denote as $a_{n,m}$ [bps] the allocated rate of the common stream $s_{n,0}$ transmitted by user n to each MEC server m . Then, in order to ensure that all MEC servers $m \in \mathcal{M}$

can successfully decode the user's n common stream $s_{n,0}$, the allocated rates $a_{n,m}$ should satisfy the following condition:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m=1}^M a_{n,m} &\leq \min_{m \in \mathcal{M}} c_{n,m} \\ &= B_n \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{G_{n,1} p_{n,0}}{G_{n,1} \sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} + \sigma^2} \right) = c_{n,1}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where the equality follows from the channel gains' ordering.

Additionally, for the Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC) to be successfully implemented at the receiver of each MEC server m , the following condition should be satisfied for each user n :

$$G_{n,1} p_{n,0} - G_{n,m} \sum_{j=1}^M p_{n,j} \geq P_n^{tol}, \quad (5)$$

where P_n^{tol} [Watt] is the corresponding receiver's SIC decoding tolerance/sensitivity. Following the ordering of the channel gains, Eq. (5) can be reduced as:

$$G_{n,1} p_{n,0} - G_{n,1} \sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} \geq P_n^{tol}. \quad (6)$$

After the decoding of the user's n common stream at each MEC server, the decoding of the corresponding private stream $s_{n,m}$ takes place at each MEC server, the achievable rate of which is calculated as:

$$r_{n,m} = B_n \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{G_{n,m} p_{n,m}}{G_{n,m} \sum_{j=1, j \neq m}^M p_{n,j} + \sigma^2} \right) [bps]. \quad (7)$$

The total achievable offloading rate from user n to MEC server m is:

$$\begin{aligned} r_{n,m}^{tot} &= a_{n,m} + r_{n,m} \\ &= a_{n,m} + B_n \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{G_{n,m} p_{n,m}}{G_{n,m} \sum_{j=1, j \neq m}^M p_{n,j} + \sigma^2} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Therefore, given that $\beta_{n,m} D_n$ [bits] are transmitted by user n to each MEC server m , then the corresponding transmission/offloading delay is defined as follows:

$$T_{n,m}^{off} = \frac{\beta_{n,m} D_n}{r_{n,m}^{tot}} [s]. \quad (9)$$

B. Computing Model

The computing model regards the remote processing of different parts of each user's n computation task at the different available MEC servers. Specifically, we denote as $f_{n,m}$ [CPU cycles/s] the computing resource that the MEC server m allocates to user n for the processing of its task, for which it holds that $\sum_{n=1}^N f_{n,m} = F_m, \forall m$, where F_m [CPU cycles/s] is the total computing resource owned by MEC server m . Given that $\beta_{n,m} \phi_n D_n$ [CPU cycles] are processed by MEC

server m for user n , then the corresponding processing delay is given by:

$$T_{n,m}^{proc} = \frac{\beta_{n,m} D_n \phi_n}{f_{n,m}} [s]. \quad (10)$$

As a result, the overall experienced delay by a user n from the computation task offloading and processing at a MEC server m is:

$$T_{n,m} = T_{n,m}^{off} + T_{n,m}^{proc}. \quad (11)$$

It should be noted that, in this paper, the delay incurred by the downlink transmission of the computed output from the MEC servers to the corresponding users is omitted since its impact on the overall delay experienced by the users is negligible [9], [12], [14]. On the one hand, the size of the computed output is usually much smaller than the input while on the other hand, the downlink transmission is subjected to less interference and is performed with significantly higher power than the uplink transmission/offloading performed by the user devices.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION, TRANSFORMATION & DECOMPOSITION

A. Problem Formulation

In this paper, our objective is to minimize the sum of the users' maximum experienced delay stemming from their computation task offloading and processing among the different MEC servers, as defined in Eq. (11). To achieve this, we jointly optimize each user's n vectors of allocated common-message rates $\mathbf{a}_n = [a_{n,1}, \dots, a_{n,m}, \dots, a_{n,M}]^T$, uplink transmission powers $\mathbf{p}_n = [p_{n,0}, p_{n,1}, \dots, p_{n,m}, \dots, p_{n,M}]^T$, computing resources $\mathbf{f}_n = [f_{n,1}, \dots, f_{n,m}, \dots, f_{n,M}]^T$, and computation task assignment ratios $\beta_n = [\beta_{n,1}, \dots, \beta_{n,m}, \dots, \beta_{n,M}]^T$ to the MEC servers. The corresponding maximum delay minimization problem to be solved is formally written as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{a}_n, \mathbf{p}_n, \mathbf{f}_n, \beta_n, \forall n} \sum_{n=1}^N \max_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \{T_{n,m}\} \quad (12a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \sum_{m=1}^M a_{n,m} \leq B_n \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{G_{n,1} p_{n,0}}{G_{n,1} \sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} + \sigma^2} \right), \forall n, \quad (12b)$$

$$G_{n,1} p_{n,0} - G_{n,1} \sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} \geq P_n^{tol}, \forall n, \quad (12c)$$

$$p_{n,0} + \sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} \leq P_n^{max}, \forall n, \quad (12d)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^N f_{n,m} \leq F_m, \forall m, \quad (12e)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{n,m} = 1, \forall n, \quad (12f)$$

$$r_{n,m}^{tot} \geq R_n^{min}, \forall n, m, \quad (12g)$$

$$a_{n,m}, p_{n,0}, p_{n,m}, f_{n,m} \geq 0, \beta_{n,m} \in [0, 1], \forall n, m, \quad (12h)$$

where P_n^{max} [Watt] and R_n^{min} [bps] are the user's n maximum power budget and minimum allowable uplink transmission/offloading rate requirement, respectively. The constraints of the

formulated optimization problem are explained as follows. Eq. (12b) and (12c) represent the required constraints over each user's n allocated common-message rates \mathbf{a}_n and powers \mathbf{p}_n , respectively, for the successful decoding and implementation of the SIC technique at the receivers of the MEC servers, as analytically described earlier in Section II. Also, Eq. (12d) constitutes each user's n maximum transmission power constraint. Eq. (12e) guarantees that the allocated computing resources by each MEC server m to the users do not exceed the corresponding MEC server's maximum computing resource availability F_m [CPU cycles/s] while Eq. (12f) ensures that each user's n computation task is fully offloaded to the available MEC servers. Eq. (12g) captures each user's n minimum acceptable offloading data rate to each MEC server m . Last, Eq. (12h) defines the feasible range of values of the optimization variables.

The optimization problem (12) is non-convex, due to the non-convexity of the objective function, while the rate \mathbf{a}_n , power \mathbf{p}_n , computing resource \mathbf{f}_n , and task offloading β_n vectors are highly coupled, complicating the derivation of a tractable solution. Thus, it is challenging to obtain a global optimum within polynomial time. In the following, we outline the procedures of equivalent transformation and decomposition of problem (12) that allow the derivation of a local minimum.

B. Problem Transformation & Optimal Conditions

Our first result allows reducing the objective function (12a) to an expression that is differentiable.

Lemma 1. *Let $\{\{a_{n,m}, p_{n,m}, f_{n,m}, \beta_{n,m}\}_m, p_{n,0}\}_n$ be an optimal solution to problem (12). Then, it holds*

$$T_{n,1} = T_{n,2} = \dots = T_{n,M}, \forall n, \quad (13)$$

where $T_{n,m} = T_{n,m}(a_{n,m}, p_{n,0}, p_{n,m}, f_{n,m}, \beta_{n,m}) = \frac{\beta_{n,m} D_n}{r_{n,m}^{tot}} + \frac{\beta_{n,m} D_n \phi_n}{f_{n,m}}$.

Proof. The proof is provided in Appendix A. \square

According to the Lemma 1, the users' overall experienced delays $T_{n,m}$ at the different MEC servers $m \in \mathcal{M}$ are equal to each other at the optimal solution point. This observation is subsequently utilized to equivalently transform the problem's objective function, as described in Lemma 2, below.

Lemma 2. *Let $\{\{a_{n,m}, p_{n,m}, f_{n,m}, \beta_{n,m}\}_m, p_{n,0}\}_n$ be an optimal solution of problem (12). Then, it holds*

$$T_{n,m} = D_n \frac{1 + \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{n,m} \frac{\phi_n}{f_{n,m}} r_{n,m}^{tot}}{\sum_{m=1}^M r_{n,m}^{tot}}, \forall n, m. \quad (14)$$

Proof. The proof is provided in Appendix B. \square

Therefore, the outcome of Lemma 2 is the transformation of the problem's objective function into a continuously differentiable function, which allows further mathematical manipulations toward obtaining a solution to the overall problem. Next, we proceed to the analysis of the optimal conditions that further simplify the initially formulated problem.

Lemma 3. *At the optimal solution of problem (12), the constraint (12b) over the common-message rate holds with equality: $\sum_{m=1}^M a_{n,m} = B_n \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{G_{n,1} p_{n,0}}{G_{n,1} \sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} + \sigma^2} \right), \forall n$.*

Proof. Lemma 3 can be easily proved by contradiction. \square

In particular, Lemma 3 implies that for an optimal choice of $a_{n,m}, \forall n, m$, the sum of total achievable offloading rates from user n to the different MEC servers is:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m=1}^M r_{n,m}^{tot} &= B_n \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{G_{n,1} p_{n,0}}{G_{n,1} \sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} + \sigma^2} \right) \\ &+ \sum_{m=1}^M B_n \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{G_{n,m} p_{n,m}}{G_{n,m} \sum_{j=1, j \neq m}^M p_{n,j} + \sigma^2} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

which should be noted that does not depend on $a_{n,m}, \forall m$.

Lemma 4. *At the optimal solution of problem (12), the constraint (12d) over the uplink transmission powers of the private messages holds with equality: $\sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} = P_n^{max} - p_{n,0}, \forall n$.*

Proof. The proof is presented in Appendix C. \square

Lemmas 3 and 4, so far, provided the optimal conditions that hold with respect to the users' allocated common-message rates and private-message uplink transmission powers. Lemma 5, below, focuses on the optimal condition that holds for the allocated computing resources to the users.

Lemma 5. *At the optimal solution of problem (12), the constraint (12e) over the allocated computing resources holds with equality: $\sum_{n=1}^N f_{n,m} = F_m, \forall m$.*

Proof. Lemma 5 can be easily proved by contradiction. \square

Owing to the preceding analysis, the initially formulated maximum delay minimization problem (12) is reformulated as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{a}_n, \mathbf{p}_n, \mathbf{f}_n, \beta_n, \forall n} \sum_{n=1}^N D_n \frac{1 + \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{n,m} \frac{\phi_n}{f_{n,m}} r_{n,m}^{tot}}{\sum_{m=1}^M r_{n,m}^{tot}} \quad (16a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \sum_{m=1}^M a_{n,m} = B_n \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{G_{n,1} p_{n,0}}{G_{n,1} \sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} + \sigma^2} \right), \forall n, \quad (16b)$$

$$p_{n,0} \geq \frac{1}{2} P_n^{max} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{P_n^{tol}}{G_{n,1}}, \forall n, \quad (16c)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} = P_n^{max} - p_{n,0}, \forall n, \quad (16d)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^N f_{n,m} = F_m, \forall m, \quad (16e)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{n,m} = 1, \forall n, \quad (16f)$$

$$r_{n,m}^{tot} \geq R_n^{min}, \forall n, m, \quad (16g)$$

$$a_{n,m}, p_{n,0}, p_{n,m}, f_{n,m} \geq 0, \beta_{n,m} \in [0, 1], \forall n, m, \quad (16h)$$

where constraint (16c) derives from (12c) following Lemma 4 and by setting $\sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} = P_n^{max} - p_{n,0}$.

C. Problem Decomposition

In this section, we exploit the structure of the equivalently transformed problem (16), which, upon combination with the KKT conditions, allows the decomposition of the problem into two independent sub-problems that can separately provide suboptimal solutions to the radio and optimal solutions to the computing resource allocation. We begin by first describing the KKT conditions corresponding to problem (16).

The Lagrangian function (see [26, Theorem 2.1]) of problem (16) can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} = & \sum_{n=1}^N \left\{ D_n \frac{1 + \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{n,m} \frac{\phi_n}{f_{n,m}} r_{n,m}^{tot}}{\sum_{m=1}^M r_{n,m}^{tot}} \right. \\ & + \lambda_n^a \left(\sum_{m=1}^M a_{n,m} - B_n \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{G_{n,1} p_{n,0}}{G_{n,1} \sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} + \sigma^2} \right) \right) \\ & + \lambda_n^0 \left(\frac{1}{2} P_n^{max} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{P_n^{tot}}{G_{n,1}} - p_{n,0} \right) + \sum_{m=1}^M \lambda_{n,m}^r \left(R_n^{min} - r_{n,m}^{tot} \right) \\ & + \lambda_n^p \left(\sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} - P_n^{max} + p_{n,0} \right) + \lambda_n^\beta \left(\sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{n,m} - 1 \right) \left. \right\} \\ & + \sum_{m=1}^M \lambda_m^f \left(\sum_{n=1}^N f_{n,m} - F_m \right), \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where for each n and m , $\lambda_n^a, \lambda_n^0, \lambda_{n,m}^r, \lambda_n^p, \lambda_n^\beta, \lambda_m^f \geq 0$ are the, so-called, Lagrange multipliers that correspond to the constraints of problem (16).

It follows from the KKT theorem (see [26, Theorem 2.1]) that if $\{a_{n,m}, p_{n,m}, f_{n,m}, \beta_{n,m}\}_m, p_{n,0}\}_n$ is a local minimum of problem (16), then there exist Lagrange multipliers $\lambda_n^a, \lambda_n^0, \lambda_{n,m}^r, \lambda_n^p, \lambda_n^\beta, \lambda_m^f$ such that

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial a_{n,m}} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{n,0}} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{n,m}} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial f_{n,m}} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \beta_{n,m}} = 0, \quad (18)$$

which is the stationary condition of the KKT conditions.

Lemma 6. *Let $\{\{a_{n,m}, p_{n,m}, f_{n,m}, \beta_{n,m}\}_m, p_{n,0}\}_n$ be a local minimum of problem (16). Then, it holds*

$$\frac{r_{n,m}^{tot}}{f_{n,m}} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^M r_{n,j}^{tot}}{\sum_{j=1}^M f_{n,j}}. \quad (19)$$

Proof. Note that Eq. (18) and the partial derivative with respect to $\beta_{n,m}$ imply that for each $m \in \mathcal{M}$ it holds $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \beta_{n,m}} = 0$, which in turn yields:

$$\frac{r_{n,1}^{tot}}{f_{n,1}} = \dots = \frac{r_{n,M}^{tot}}{f_{n,M}} = -\lambda_n^\beta. \quad (20)$$

Let m be fixed and for each $j \neq m$ let $t_j = \frac{r_{n,j}^{tot}}{r_{n,m}^{tot}} = \frac{f_{n,j}}{f_{n,m}}$. Then, Eq. (20) implies that

$$\frac{r_{n,m}^{tot}}{f_{n,m}} = \frac{r_{n,m}^{tot} \cdot (1 + \sum_{j \neq m} t_j)}{f_{n,m} \cdot (1 + \sum_{j \neq m} t_j)} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^M r_{n,j}^{tot}}{\sum_{j=1}^M f_{n,j}}, \quad (21)$$

completing the proof. \square

Now, using Eq. (19) and the fact that $\sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{n,m} = 1$, we may write each addend in the objective function (16a) as:

$$\begin{aligned} T_{n,m} &= D_n \frac{1 + \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{n,m} \frac{\phi_n}{f_{n,m}} r_{n,m}^{tot}}{\sum_{m=1}^M r_{n,m}^{tot}} \\ &= \frac{D_n}{\sum_{m=1}^M r_{n,m}^{tot}} + \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{n,m} D_n \phi_n \frac{\sum_{j=1}^M r_{n,j}^{tot}}{\sum_{j=1}^M f_{n,j}}}{\sum_{m=1}^M r_{n,m}^{tot}} \\ &= \frac{D_n}{\sum_{m=1}^M r_{n,m}^{tot}} + \frac{D_n \phi_n}{\sum_{m=1}^M f_{n,m}}. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Observe that the first term of Eq. (22) depends only on $\{p_{n,0}, \{p_{n,m}\}_m\}_n$ and thus, indirectly on $\{a_{n,m}\}_{n,m}$, whereas the second term depends only on $\{f_{n,m}\}_{n,m}$. Consequently, the transformed problem (16) is further decomposed into two independent optimization problems.

First, given the assumption that different users utilize different frequency bands to accommodate their computation task offloading and thus, their transmissions do not interfere with each other, it suffices to solve N independent problems to derive each user's n optimal common-message rate \mathbf{a}_n^* and uplink transmission power \mathbf{p}_n^* vectors. Based on the first term of Eq. (22), the corresponding optimization problem may be written as the maximization of each user's n sum of total achievable offloading rates to the different MEC servers. The solution to this problem will be discussed later in Section IV-C, while its formal description is as follows:

$$\max_{\substack{a_{n,m}, p_{n,0}, \\ p_{n,m} \geq 0, \forall m}} \sum_{m=1}^M r_{n,m}^{tot} \quad (23a)$$

$$\text{s.t. (16b), (16c), (16d), (16g).} \quad (23b)$$

Regarding the derivation of each user's n optimal computing resource allocation \mathbf{f}_n^* vector, it suffices to solve the following problem:

$$\min_{f_{n,m} \geq 0, \forall n, m} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{D_n \phi_n}{\sum_{m=1}^M f_{n,m}} \quad (24a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \sum_{n=1}^N f_{n,m} = F_m, \forall m. \quad (24b)$$

The closed-form solution of problem (24) and the procedure that results in this solution are detailed later in Section IV-B.

IV. DELAY MINIMIZATION SOLUTION FOR RSMA-BASED MULTI-SERVER MEC SYSTEMS

In this section, we present the proposed solution to the joint computation task offloading and radio and computing resource allocation problem. First, in Section IV-A, the users' optimal computation task assignment ratios to the different MEC servers are determined, based on the preceding analysis of equivalent problem transformation and decomposition. Then, the optimal solution to the computing resource allocation problem (24) is derived using the KKT conditions (Section IV-B), while an iterative algorithm is utilized to lead to a suboptimal solution for the joint rate and uplink transmission power problem (23) (Section IV-C). The section concludes

with the algorithm description of the overall proposed solution and its complexity analysis (Section IV-D).

A. Computation Task Assignment

The overall problem transformation and decomposition analysis presented in the previous section is founded on the basis that, in the optimal solution, the users' experienced delays related to different MEC servers are equal to each other, i.e., $T_{n,1} = T_{n,2} = \dots = T_{n,M}, \forall n, m$. Particularly, in Lemma 1, it has been proved that to minimize each user's n maximum experienced delay among the different MEC servers, each user's vector of computation task offloading assignment ratios β^* will be optimized such that the equalization of the experienced delays related to different MEC servers is achieved. Lemma 7, below, provides the optimal solution to this problem along with insights on how to obtain this solution.

Lemma 7. *Let $\{\{a_{n,m}, p_{n,m}, f_{n,m}, \beta_{n,m}^*\}_m, p_{n,0}\}_n$ be a local minimum of problem (16). Then, each user's n optimal computation task assignment ratio to MEC server m is:*

$$\beta_{n,m}^* = \frac{\frac{r_{n,m}^{tot} \cdot f_{n,m}}{f_{n,m} + \phi_n r_{n,m}^{tot}}}{\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{r_{n,m}^{tot} \cdot f_{n,m}}{f_{n,m} + \phi_n r_{n,m}^{tot}}}, \forall n, m, \quad (25)$$

satisfying the conditions $\beta_{n,m}^* \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{n,m}^* = 1$.

Proof. From the general definition of each user's n overall experienced delay $T_{n,m}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_{n,m} &= \frac{\beta_{n,m} D_n}{r_{n,m}^{tot}} + \frac{\beta_{n,m} D_n \phi_n}{f_{n,m}} \\ &= D_n \beta_{n,m} \frac{f_{n,m} + \phi_n r_{n,m}^{tot}}{r_{n,m}^{tot} \cdot f_{n,m}}. \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Furthermore, Eq. (22) implies that

$$\begin{aligned} T_{n,m} &= \frac{D_n}{\sum_{m=1}^M r_{n,m}^{tot}} + \frac{D_n \phi_n}{\sum_{m=1}^M f_{n,m}} \\ &= \frac{D_n}{\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{r_{n,m}^{tot}}{1 + \phi_n \frac{\sum_{j=1}^M r_{n,j}^{tot}}{\sum_{j=1}^M f_{n,j}}}} \\ \text{Eq. (19)} &= \frac{D_n}{\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{r_{n,m}^{tot}}{1 + \phi_n \frac{r_{n,m}^{tot}}{f_{n,m}}}} \\ &= \frac{D_n}{\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{r_{n,m}^{tot} \cdot f_{n,m}}{f_{n,m} + \phi_n r_{n,m}^{tot}}}. \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

By setting Eq. (26) and (27) equal to each other and solving with respect to $\beta_{n,m}$, the result of Lemma 7 follows. \square

B. Computing Resource Allocation

In the following, the solution to problem (24) is derived, which provides the optimal computing resource allocation vectors \mathbf{f}_n^* for all users $n \in \mathcal{N}$ in the system.

Lemma 8. *Let $\{f_{n,m}^*\}_{n,m}$ be a global minimum of problem (24). Then, each user's n optimal computing resource allocation by each MEC server m is:*

$$f_{n,m}^* = F_m \frac{\sqrt{D_n \phi_n}}{\sum_{j=1}^N \sqrt{D_j \phi_j}}, \forall n, m. \quad (28)$$

Proof. We begin by considering the following more general problem:

$$\min_{z_n \geq 0, \forall n} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{D_n \phi_n}{z_n} \quad (29a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{n=1}^N z_n = \sum_{m=1}^M F_m, \quad (29b)$$

which is obtained by setting $z_n = \sum_{m=1}^M f_{n,m}, \forall n$, in problem (24). The constraints of problem (29) are convex, while it can be easily found that the objective function (29a) is also convex by verifying that the corresponding Hessian is positive definite. As a result, problem (29) is convex and a globally optimal solution can be obtained using the KKT conditions (see [26, Theorem 3.8]). The Lagrange function of problem (29) is given by:

$$\Lambda = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{D_n \phi_n}{z_n} + \lambda \left(\sum_{n=1}^N z_n - \sum_{m=1}^M F_m \right), \quad (30)$$

where $\lambda \geq 0$ is the corresponding Lagrange multiplier of constraint (29b). From the stationary condition $\frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial z_n} = 0, \forall n$, we get that $\frac{D_n \phi_n}{z_n^2} = \lambda, \forall n$, and therefore it holds

$$z_n = \sqrt{\frac{D_n \phi_n}{\lambda}}, \forall n. \quad (31)$$

In particular, considering Eq. (29b), this implies that

$$\sum_{m=1}^M F_m = \sum_{n=1}^N z_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}} \sum_{n=1}^N \sqrt{D_n \phi_n}, \quad (32)$$

and a global optimal solution of problem (29) follows as:

$$z_n^* = \left(\sum_{m=1}^M F_m \right) \frac{\sqrt{D_n \phi_n}}{\sum_{j=1}^N \sqrt{D_j \phi_j}}, \forall n. \quad (33)$$

Now, set $f_{n,m}^* = F_m \frac{\sqrt{D_n \phi_n}}{\sum_{j=1}^N \sqrt{D_j \phi_j}}, \forall n, m$ and obtain each user's n optimal computing resource allocation by the different MEC servers.

It is straightforward to verify that the points $\{f_{n,m}^*\}_{n,m}$ belong to the feasible region of problem (24), and that the objective function (24a) evaluated at the points given by Eq. (28) is equal to the function (29a) evaluated at the points given by Eq. (33). Summarizing the above, we conclude that the points defined in Eq. (28) constitute a global minimum of problem (24). \square

C. Rate & Uplink Transmission Power Allocation

Considering each user's n optimal common-message rate \mathbf{a}_n^* and uplink transmission power \mathbf{p}_n^* vectors, these are determined by solving problem (23), independently for each user. The analytic formal presentation of the corresponding optimization problem to be solved for each user is written as:

$$\max_{\substack{a_{n,m}, p_{n,0}, \\ p_{n,m} \geq 0, \forall m}} \sum_{m=1}^M r_{n,m}^{tot} \quad (34a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \sum_{m=1}^M a_{n,m} = B_n \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{G_{n,1} p_{n,0}}{G_{n,1} \sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} + \sigma^2} \right), \quad (34b)$$

$$p_{n,0} \geq \frac{1}{2} P_n^{max} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{P_n^{tol}}{G_{n,1}}, \quad (34c)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} = P_n^{max} - p_{n,0}, \quad (34d)$$

$$r_{n,m}^{tot} \geq R_n^{min}, \forall m. \quad (34e)$$

From the definition of problem (34), it can be easily concluded that it resembles the typical sum rate maximization problem in the downlink communication scenario between a single BS and multiple users, where the transmissions from the BS to the different users are multiplexed via the RSMA technique. Therefore, given the intensive efforts in the literature so far in the domain of RSMA-based wireless communications, an analytic solution to the latter problem exists and can be found in [15]. In this paper, we capitalize on the analogy between the single-user multi-server MEC system and the single-BS multi-user communications system and borrow the common rate and uplink transmission power allocation solution introduced in [15]. In the following, we summarize the respective solution as applied in our RSMA-based multi-server MEC system, while the interested reader may refer to [15] for the details.

In detail, owing to problem's (34) non-convexity, it is generally hard to directly optimize the parameters $a_{n,m}, p_{n,m}, \forall m$ and $p_{n,0}$ of each user n , and for this reason, an iterative optimization procedure is followed. First, considering that each user's n common-message rates $a_{n,m}, \forall m$ and uplink transmission power $p_{n,0}$ are fixed, its optimal uplink transmission powers $p_{n,m}^*$ of the private messages to the different MEC servers are determined according to Lemma 9 below.

Lemma 9 (see [15], Theorems 1 and 2). *Let $\{\{a_{n,m}, p_{n,m}^*\}_m, p_{n,0}\}_n$ be a local maximum of problem (34). Then, there exists $m_0 \in \mathcal{M}$ such that each user's n optimal uplink transmission power of the private message to each MEC server m is:*

$$p_{n,m}^* = \begin{cases} p_{n,m}^{min}, & \text{if } m \neq m_0, \\ P_n^{max} - p_{n,0} - \sum_{m \neq m_0} p_{n,m}^{min}, & \text{if } m = m_0, \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

$$\text{where } p_{n,m}^{min} = \left(1 - 2^{\frac{a_{n,m} - R_n^{min}}{B_n}} \right) \cdot \left(P_n^{max} - p_{n,0} + \frac{\sigma^2}{G_{n,m}} \right)$$

$$\text{and } m_0 = \arg \min_{m \in \mathcal{M}} 2^{\frac{a_{n,m} - R_n^{min}}{B_n}} \left(P_n^{max} - p_{n,0} + \frac{\sigma^2}{G_{n,m}} \right).$$

From Lemma 9, it can be deduced that each user's n optimal solutions $p_{n,m}^*, \forall m$ are equal to the minimum acceptable uplink transmission powers $p_{n,m}^{min}$ that meet the user's minimum offloading rate requirement in Eq. (34e), except for one MEC server $m_0 \in \mathcal{M}$, the wireless link between which and the user n is allocated the whole amount of the remaining power of the user n from P_n^{max} . The purpose of the latter is to allow the maximization of the user's n sum of total offloading rates to the different MEC servers. Consequently, the MEC server m_0 that is specifically selected for this purpose is determined as $m_0 = \arg \max_{m \in \mathcal{M}} r_{n,m}^{tot}$, which by substitution of Eq. (35) gives

$$m_0 = \arg \min_{m \in \mathcal{M}} 2^{\frac{a_{n,m} - R_n^{min}}{B_n}} \left(P_n^{max} - p_{n,0} + \frac{\sigma^2}{G_{n,m}} \right).$$

Given each user's n optimal uplink transmission powers $p_{n,m}^*, \forall m$ of the private messages and considering the corresponding common-message power $p_{n,0}$ as fixed, the user's n optimal common-message rates $a_{n,m}^*$ to the different MEC servers are obtained as described in Lemma 10, below.

Lemma 10 (see [15], Theorem 3). *Let $\{\{a_{n,m}^*, p_{n,m}\}_m, p_{n,0}\}_n$ be local maximum of problem (34). Considering the different MEC servers sorted in ascending order as per the channel gains between them and the user n , i.e., $G_{n,1} \leq \dots \leq G_{n,m} \leq \dots \leq G_{n,M}$, each user's n optimal common-message rate to each MEC server m is:*

i) if $c_1 < M \cdot R_n^{min}$:

$$a_{n,m}^* = \begin{cases} R_n^{min}, & \text{if } m < l, \\ c_1 - (l-1) \cdot R_n^{min}, & \text{if } m = l, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

where l satisfies $(l-1) \cdot R_n^{min} \leq c_1 \leq l \cdot R_n^{min}$ with $0 \leq l < M$, and c_1 is as defined in Eq. (4).

ii) if $c_1 \geq M \cdot R_n^{min}$:

$$a_{n,m}^* = R_n^{min}, \forall m. \quad (37)$$

Lemma 10 indicates that it is optimal to allocate more rate to the wireless links between the user and the MEC servers of lower channel gains, and equal in amount to the user's minimum offloading rate requirement R_n^{min} , enabling in this way the maximization of the user's n sum of total offloading rates to the different MEC servers. Also, given the obtained solution $a_{n,m}^*$, we can return to Lemma 9 and observe that the specific m_0 that should be selected is equal to $m_0 = M$. In other words, the wireless link between user n and MEC server M that is characterized by the maximum channel gain $G_{n,M}$ is optimal to be allocated more power.

Given the solution $a_{n,m}^*, \forall m$, the user's n optimal uplink transmission power $p_{n,0}^*$ of the common message to the different MEC servers is, then, calculated as follows.

Lemma 11 (see [15], Theorem 5). *Let $\{\{a_{n,m}, p_{n,m}\}_m, p_{n,0}\}_n$ be a local maximum of problem (34). Then, each user's*

n optimal uplink transmission power of the common message to the MEC servers is:

$$p_{n,0}^* \in \left\{ \frac{1}{2} P_n^{max} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{P_n^{tol}}{G_{n,1}}, \left(1 - 2^{-\sum_{m=1}^M a_{n,m}} \right) \cdot \left(P_n^{max} + \frac{\sigma^2}{G_{n,1}} \right), P_{n,0} \right\} \quad (38)$$

where $P_{n,0}$ satisfies the following condition:

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \left(1 - 2^{\frac{a_{n,m} - R_n^{min}}{B_n}} \right) \cdot \left(P_n^{max} - P_{n,0} + \frac{\sigma^2}{G_{n,m}} \right) = P_n^{max} - P_{n,0}. \quad (39)$$

Practically, Lemma 11 implies that the user's n optimal uplink transmission power $p_{n,0}^*$ of its common message to the different MEC servers is equal to one out of the candidate values defined in the discrete set of Eq. (38), which results in the maximum sum of the total offloading rates, i.e., the maximum value of the objective function (34a).

D. Algorithm Overview

The overall solution to the joint task offloading and radio and computing resource allocation problem scrutinized in this paper under the RSMA-based multi-server MEC system, while targeting the sum of users' maximum experienced delay minimization, is analytically presented in Algorithm 1. Especially, lines 6-10 of Algorithm 1, illustrate the iterative procedure that is followed to obtain the optimal common-message rate and uplink transmission power for each user. Considering that the solutions of all optimized parameters are given in closed forms, the complexity of the overall Algorithm 1 is $\mathcal{O}(NMT)$, where T denotes the number of iterations required for the iterative procedure in lines 6-10 to converge. Indicative numerical results regarding the real execution time required for Algorithm 1 to converge are presented in Section V.

Algorithm 1 Joint Task Offloading, and Radio and Computing Resource Allocation in RSMA-based multi-server MEC systems

- 1: Initialize $\sigma^2, B_n, P_n^{tol}, P_n^{max}, R_n^{min}, D_n, \phi_n, G_{n,m}, F_m, \forall n, m$.
 - 2: Determine $f_{n,m}^*, \forall n, m$ based on Lemma 8 and Eq. (28).
 - 3: Determine $\beta_{n,m}^*, \forall n, m$ based on Lemma 7 and Eq. (25).
 - 4: **for** $n \in \mathcal{N}$ **do**
 - 5: Initialize $a_{n,m}^{(0)}, \forall m, p_{n,0}^{(0)}$ and set $t = 1$.
 - 6: **repeat**
 - 7: Given $p_{n,0}^{(t-1)}$, determine $a_{n,m}^{(t)}, \forall m$ based on Lemma 10 and Eq. (36)-(37).
 - 8: Given $a_{n,m}^{(t)}, \forall m$, determine $p_{n,0}^{(t)}$ based on Lemma 11 and Eq. (38).
 - 9: Set $t = t + 1$.
 - 10: **until** the objective value (34a) converges.
 - 11: Set $a_{n,m}^* = a_{n,m}^{(t)}, \forall m$ and $p_{n,0}^* = p_{n,0}^{(t)}, \forall m$.
 - 12: Derive $p_{n,m}^*, \forall m$ based on Lemma 9 and Eq. (35).
 - 13: **end for**
-

V. EVALUATION & RESULTS

In this section, the performance of the proposed solution for the joint task offloading and radio and computing resource allocation in RSMA-based multi-server MEC systems is evaluated via modeling and simulation. Throughout our simulation experiments, we consider N users randomly and uniformly distributed in a square area of size 150×150 m. The users concurrently offload part of their computation tasks to M MEC servers spatially uniformly located within this area. The channel gain between user n and MEC server m is calculated based on the distance-based path loss model $PL = 128.1 + 37.6 \log_{10}(d)$, with d measured in km, while the standard deviation of the shadow fading is 4 dB [9], [15]. Depending on the simulation setup, different values of the overall system bandwidth B [Hz] are considered, while the rest of the communication-related parameters are set as $\sigma^2 = -104$ dB, $P_n^{max} = 24$ dBm, $R_n^{min} = 1$ Mbps and $P_n^{tol} = -94$ dBm, $\forall n \in \mathcal{N}$, unless otherwise explicitly stated. The input data size of each user is $D_n = 2$ Mbits, while the value of its computation task size C_n [CPU cycles] varies depending on the simulation setup and the system density. The computing resource availability of the MEC servers is considered as $F_m = 5$ GHz, $\forall m \in \mathcal{M}$. The simulation results have been averaged over 3000 different channel realizations.

First, to characterize and evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed solution, we compare its performance against the solution of the Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP) iterative algorithm used in constrained non-linear optimization [27]. SQP algorithm is widely implemented as part of the optimization toolbox of different programming platforms, such as MATLAB [28], and, in this evaluation scenario, is used to solve the initially formulated min-max-sum problem (12). Due to the high complexity of the original problem (12) and the inability of the SQP algorithm to result in a stable and feasible solution as the number of users and MEC servers increases, the comparison is carried out in a small system of $B = 5$ MHz overall bandwidth with $N = [2, 5]$ users, the computation task size of which is set equal to $C_n = 2000$ Mega-CPU cycles. The outcome of the comparison between the SQP algorithm (labeled as "SQP") and Algorithm 1 (labeled as "Proposed") is reported in Fig. 2. In particular, Fig. 2a illustrates the sum of the users' maximum experienced delay among the different MEC servers (vertical axis) that is defined in Eq. (12a), as a function of the number of users (horizontal axis) and MEC servers (different graph coloring), whereas Fig. 2b examines the real execution time in seconds required for each one of the proposed and SQP algorithms to obtain a solution (vertical axis) under different user and MEC server numbers.

The numerical results reveal that for particularly small systems with $N = 2$ or $N = 3$ users, the two algorithms present comparable performance regarding the minimum achievable value of the optimization objective (Fig. 2a). On the contrary, as the number of users increases, the proposed algorithm manages to conclude at lower sums of the users' maximum experienced delay among the different MEC servers than the SQP, while this performance gap between the two algorithms diminishes as the number of MEC servers increases. This is

Fig. 2: Comparison between the proposed and SQP algorithms' solutions in terms of the (a) sum of users' maximum experienced delay, and (b) real execution time.

Fig. 3: Pure performance evaluation of the proposed solution in terms of the users' (a) overall experienced delay, (b) mean offloading delay, and (c) mean processing delay.

owed to the fact that for a small number of MEC servers, the SQP algorithm can quickly pinpoint a local minimum of the problem by potentially sacrificing the minimization procedure's performance. The latter is further corroborated in Fig. 2b, where it is demonstrated that the real execution time required for the SQP algorithm to lead to a solution is increasing proportionally to both the number of users and MEC servers in the system, being faster than the proposed algorithm for $M = 2$ and slower for $M = 3$ or $M = 4$. At this point, it is quite interesting to observe that although the proposed algorithm's complexity is a function of both N and M (see Section IV-D), its real execution time is steered by the for loop initiated in line 4 of Algorithm 1, and thus is mainly affected by the number of users existing in the system. Consequently, its real execution time gets gradually higher for more users in the system but remains unchanged as the number of servers increases. Concluding, the proposed algorithm strikes a good balance between the users' achieved maximum experienced delay and the real execution time.

Subsequently, we aim to evaluate the pure performance of the proposed solution under a large-scale system and interpret the operation of this multi-server MEC system in terms of the individual offloading and processing delays as the number of users and MEC servers increases. In this simulation setup, the overall system bandwidth is set equal to $B = 20$ MHz,

and the number of users and servers varies in the intervals $N = [10, 50]$ and $M = [1, 4]$, while each user's computation task size is set as $C_n = 80$ Mega-CPU cycles. Fig. 3 depicts the mean values of the users' (a) overall experienced delays as defined in Eq. (14), (b) mean offloading delays to the different MEC servers, and (c) mean processing delays at the different MEC servers. Apparently, considering a fixed number of MEC servers, the higher the number of users existing in the system, then the higher their overall experienced delay is. The inverse behavior is observed as the number of MEC servers increases, given a fixed number of users. The rationale behind this operation is as follows. Considering that the MEC servers are spatially uniformly distributed within the square area, the denser this area becomes with the number of MEC servers increasing from $M = 2$ to $M = 4$, the users are getting closer to the MEC servers and achieve higher data rates (see Fig. 4), while the overall system's computing capacity increases at the same time. For this reason, both the users' mean offloading and processing delay at the different MEC servers decrease. Concerning the special case, when a single MEC server exists in the system (i.e., $M = 1$), Fig. 3b shows that a lower offloading delay is achieved compared to the multi-server MEC case since the users utilize the whole available bandwidth $B_n = \frac{B}{N}$ [Hz] to them without splitting it to accommodate multiple concurrent transmissions. This

Fig. 4: Pure performance evaluation of the proposed solution in terms of the users' total data rate.

behavior is further corroborated by the results in Fig. 4 where it is implied that a higher offloading data rate per server is achieved by the users under the single-MEC server case. Nevertheless, given the high computing demands of the users, a significantly higher processing delay is caused in the single-server case than the multi-server case, which dominates and results in low overall experienced delays on the users' side for the latter. This highlights the superiority and benefits of multi-server to single-server MEC offloading in dense and high-computing demands systems.

To further identify the performance gains of an RSMA-based multi-server MEC system regarding the users' experienced delay, we compare its performance against the equivalent NOMA-based implementation in [14] and an OFDMA-based implementation, whose solution of problem (23) follows the work in [29]. The comparison is performed considering the same simulation setup as in Fig. 3, while an indicative number of $N = 40$ users and $M = 3$ MEC servers is selected. In Table I, the mean values of the users' overall experienced delays (as defined in Eq. (14)) are summarized, considering different values of the minimum acceptable offloading data rate R_n^{min} to the MEC servers. As the minimum data rate demand R_n^{min} increases, the users' experienced delay ameliorates both in the RSMA and NOMA-based MEC systems, while the RSMA-based MEC system yields at average 28 ms lower experienced delays to the users compared to the NOMA-based one in all examined R_n^{min} cases. The OFDMA-based MEC system operates only under very low R_n^{min} demands, i.e., $R_n^{min} = 0.5$ Mbps, for the given available bandwidth, number of users and servers, where its performance surpasses the RSMA and NOMA-based systems. The latter is justified by the fact that, in OFDMA, each separate transmission/offloading is performed over a distinct frequency band that does not interfere with any other, resulting in a higher data rate and thus, lower users' experienced delay.

The results indicate that the RSMA-based system proves to be the only one among the rest of the alternatives that can provide a solution to the sum rate maximization problem (23) for increasing values of R_n^{min} up to 2 Mbps which is attributed to the intelligent control between decoding interference and treating interference as noise. Specifically, when employing power-domain NOMA, each transmission of a user to a

TABLE I: Comparison among RSMA, NOMA, and OFDMA-based schemes in terms of the users' overall experienced delay, under different values of R_n^{min} .

Technique	R_n^{min}			
	0.5 Mbps	0.75 Mbps	1 Mbps	1.25 Mbps
RSMA	0.6194	0.5570	0.5117	0.4777
NOMA	0.6398	0.5827	0.5404	0.5082
OFDMA	0.5143	-	-	-
<hr/>				
Technique	1.5 Mbps	1.75 Mbps	2 Mbps	
	RSMA	0.4521	0.4333	0.4229
NOMA	0.4852	-	-	
OFDMA	-	-	-	

MEC server senses the interference that stems from all other transmissions to the MEC servers for which the user-to-MEC-server channel gain is higher, making it hard to reach the minimum acceptable data rate requirement R_n^{min} . On the other hand, the inability of the implementation under the OFDMA technique to achieve a high value for the minimum acceptable data rate lies in the total available bandwidth fragmentation to N equal portions allocated to each user individually, each of which is then divided into M portions to facilitate the computation task offloading to the M different MEC servers.

Fig. 5 illustrates the mean values of the users' experienced delays under the RSMA, NOMA, and OFDMA techniques, but this time considering different values of the users' maximum power budget P_n^{max} . As the users' power budget P_n^{max} increases, they can achieve higher offloading rates and thus, experience lower delays (left sub-figure) under all comparative multiple access techniques, while the RSMA-based solution provides constantly better performance. Fig. 5, also, reveals the significant impact that the maximum power budget P_n^{max} has on the performance of the OFDMA-based system, where the optimal solution for each user is to equally allocate its power to the different offloading MEC servers, i.e., $\frac{P_n^{max}}{M}$, and maximize the individual data rates to the servers since no interference exists between them. This effect is claimed by the sharp decrease in the users' experienced delays as their power budget gets higher (left sub-figure), which is further justified by the behavior of the users' minimum achievable data rate among the different MEC servers at the right sub-figure.

VI. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have proposed the application of the novel RSMA technique to accommodate the concurrent task offloading of the users in a multi-server MEC system. Particularly, we have investigated the problem of minimizing the sum of the users' maximum experienced delays, stemming from both the computation task offloading and processing at the different MEC servers, by jointly optimizing the computation task assignment and radio and computing resource allocation related to each offloading MEC server of the users. The initially formulated min-max-sum problem has been equivalently transformed and decomposed into two independent sub-problems, namely the rate and power allocation and the computing resource allocation problems, while the optimal solution of computation task assignment has been naturally

Fig. 5: Comparison between RSMA, NOMA, and OFDMA-based schemes in terms of the users' (a) overall experienced delay, and (b) min data rate, under different values of P_n^{max} .

derived from the aforementioned transformation and decomposition procedure. The proposed solution has been proved to be highly efficient in terms of complexity and experienced delay by the users compared to conventional non-linear optimization algorithms. Its effectiveness has also been demonstrated after comprehensive comparison against state-of-the-art approaches, where different multiple access techniques are applied.

Our future work aims to study the application of ML techniques, such as deep reinforcement learning, and target the solution of similar optimization problems in RSMA-based MEC systems, by incorporating this form of intelligence in the solution procedure.

APPENDIX A PROOF OF LEMMA 1

Lemma 1 is proved by contradiction. Let $\{\{a_{n,m}, p_{n,m}, f_{n,m}, \beta_{n,m}\}_m, p_{n,0}\}_n$ be an optimal solution of problem (12), for which, without loss of generality, it holds

$$T_{n,1}(a_{n,1}, p_{n,1}, f_{n,1}, \beta_{n,1}) > T_{n,2}(a_{n,2}, p_{n,2}, f_{n,2}, \beta_{n,2}), \quad (40)$$

for some $n \in \mathcal{N}$. This implies that there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that

$$T_{n,1}(a_{n,1}, p_{n,1}, f_{n,1}, \beta_{n,1} - \varepsilon) > T_{n,2}(a_{n,2}, p_{n,2}, f_{n,2}, \beta_{n,2} + \varepsilon), \quad (41)$$

and thus we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} T_{n,1}(a_{n,1}, p_{n,1}, f_{n,1}, \beta_{n,1}) &> T_{n,1}(a_{n,1}, p_{n,1}, f_{n,1}, \beta_{n,1} - \varepsilon) \\ &> T_{n,2}(a_{n,2}, p_{n,2}, f_{n,2}, \beta_{n,2} + \varepsilon). \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

In particular, we conclude that if we replace the points $\beta_{n,1}, \beta_{n,2}$ with the points $\beta_{n,1} - \varepsilon, \beta_{n,2} + \varepsilon$, we then obtain a point belonging to the feasible region for which the objective function decreases, contrarily to the assumption that the points $\beta_{n,1}, \beta_{n,2}$ are optimal.

APPENDIX B PROOF OF LEMMA 2

From Lemma 1, we have proved that at the optimal solution point, it holds that $T_{n,1} = \dots = T_{n,M}, \forall n$, which may equivalently be written as:

$$\frac{\beta_{n,1} D_n + \frac{\beta_{n,1} D_n \phi_n}{f_{n,1}} r_{n,1}^{tot}}{r_{n,1}^{tot}} = \dots = \frac{\beta_{n,M} D_n + \frac{\beta_{n,M} D_n \phi_n}{f_{n,M}} r_{n,M}^{tot}}{r_{n,M}^{tot}}. \quad (43)$$

Now observe that for each $m \in \{2, \dots, M\}$ it holds

$$t_m = \frac{\beta_{n,m} D_n + \frac{\beta_{n,m} D_n \phi_n}{f_{n,m}} r_{n,m}^{tot}}{\beta_{n,1} D_n + \frac{\beta_{n,1} D_n \phi_n}{f_{n,1}} r_{n,1}^{tot}} = \frac{r_{n,m}^{tot}}{r_{n,1}^{tot}}, \quad (44)$$

which, in turn, implies that

$$\begin{aligned} T_{n,1} &= D_n \frac{\beta_{n,1} + \beta_{n,1} \frac{\phi_n}{f_{n,1}} r_{n,1}^{tot}}{r_{n,1}^{tot}} \\ &= D_n \frac{\left(\beta_{n,1} + \beta_{n,1} \frac{\phi_n}{f_{n,1}} r_{n,1}^{tot}\right) \cdot (1 + t_2 + \dots + t_M)}{r_{n,1}^{tot} \cdot (1 + t_2 + \dots + t_M)} \\ &= D_n \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M \left(\beta_{n,m} + \beta_{n,m} \frac{\phi_n}{f_{n,m}} r_{n,m}^{tot}\right)}{\sum_{m=1}^M r_{n,m}^{tot}} \\ &= D_n \frac{1 + \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{n,m} \frac{\phi_n}{f_{n,m}} r_{n,m}^{tot}}{\sum_{m=1}^M r_{n,m}^{tot}}, \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

where the last equality follows from $\sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{n,m} = 1$. Since $T_{n,1} = \dots = T_{n,M}$ the result follows.

APPENDIX C PROOF OF LEMMA 4

Let $p_{n,i}, i \in \mathcal{M}$, be an optimal solution of problem (12). Suppose, towards arriving at a contradiction, that $\sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} < P_n^{max} - p_{n,0}$. Set $\alpha = \frac{P_n^{max}}{P_n^{max} - \sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m}}$, and note that $\alpha > 1$. Now, define $p_{n,i}^* = \alpha p_{n,i}$, for $i \in \mathcal{M}$. It can be easily noticed if we replace the values $p_{n,i}, i \in \mathcal{M}$ in the optimal solution with the values $p_{n,i}^*, i \in \mathcal{M}$, then the objective function decreases. Furthermore, since it holds that

$$\begin{aligned} p_{n,0}^* - \sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m}^* &= \alpha \cdot \left(p_{n,0} - \sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} \right) \\ &> p_{n,0} - \sum_{m=1}^M p_{n,m} \geq \frac{P_n^{tol}}{G_{n,1}}, \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

the points $p_{n,i}^*, i \in \{0, 1, \dots, M\}$, belong to the feasible region of problem (12), thus contradicting the assumption that $p_{n,i}, i \in \{0, 1, \dots, M\}$, is optimal.

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